

Using the Nominal Operating Point as a Design Variable for Gain Scheduled Controllers

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Abstract

One approach to designing gain scheduled controllers is to decompose them into an inner loop scheduled so that the closed inner loop response is as close as possible to some nominal plant response and an unscheduled outer loop designed using the nominal plant. The choice of nominal plant/operating point is traditionally based on engineering judgment and experience. Rather than the usual approach of designing controllers for several operating points and interpolating between them, the authors have proposed a different procedure in which the parametric form of the controller is specified and parameter values are directly computed to minimize deviation from nominal over the entire operating range. This work presents an extension in which the nominal operating point is allowed to vary as an additional design variable in the optimization. This approach is applied to design of the F-18 longitudinal controller inner equalization loop. The resulting controller has significantly better consistency as compared to an existing design created using the old approach.

1. Introduction

Many systems exhibit variations in their dynamics as certain external parameters change. If these parameters change relatively slowly, they can be used to vary the parameters in the system's controller so that the controller can adapt to the system dynamics. This is known as gain scheduling.

The basic objective of gain scheduling is to compensate for the changes in plant dynamics so that the overall system has consistent response independent of the operating point. In other words, given a *nominal operating point*, we want to design the controller to minimize the *gain schedule error*, the difference between the closed loop response of the system at the nominal operating point and the response throughout the rest of the envelope.

One approach to designing gain scheduled controllers is to decompose the controller into inner and outer loops [1]. The inner loop controller is scheduled so that the closed inner loop response is as close as possible to the nominal plant response over the expected operating range. The outer loop can then be designed using the nominal plant and hence does not need to be scheduled. The traditional procedure begins with choosing the nominal plant/operating point on the basis of engineering judgment and experience. Once the nominal plant is selected, the inner loop controller is designed by picking a selection of operating points, designing a controller for each point to minimize deviation from the nominal, and selecting an interpolation scheme or fitting a parameter variation function to define the controller between the operating points [4, 5]. This is essentially a point design approach.

The authors have proposed a global procedure in which the parametric form of the controller is specified and parameter values are directly computed to minimize the inner loop response deviation over the entire operating range [6]. This

Figure 1: Outer Control Loop

work presents an extension in which the nominal operating point is allowed to vary as an additional design variable in the optimization. This approach is applied to design of the F-18 longitudinal controller inner equalization loop and the results compared to an existing design created using the traditional approach [1]. The additional degree of freedom afforded by varying the nominal operating point results in significantly more consistent closed loop response.

2. F-18 Example

The aircraft dynamics were derived from six non-linear equations of motion. Simplifying assumptions were made to decouple the equations into longitudinal and lateral-directional parts. The simplified equations were then only a function of altitude and Mach number. Since dynamic pressure closely approximates the complex variations in the plant dynamics, it was selected as the scheduling variable for the controller. The flight envelope is shown in Fig. 3. The corresponding range of dynamic pressure is 0 to 1000 psf.

The control of the F-18 longitudinal dynamics is decomposed into an inner and outer loop (See Fig. 2 and Fig. 1). The objective of the inner loop is to equalize the closed loop frequency response over the operating envelope so that the outer loop controller does not need to be scheduled. The original design selected twelve operating points, shown in Fig. 3, at which to design an inner loop controller. At each design point a minimal H_∞ controller was designed [2]. The original designers chose the nominal operating point of Mach 0.95 and altitude 20000 feet based on engineering judgment [1]. This corresponds to a dynamic pressure of 614 psf. The closed inner loop of this nominal operating point, P_0 , was used to design the outer loop controller, K_{out} . A schedule for the inner loop controller was designed by performing a linear fit of the point designed controllers.

Figure 2: Inner Control Loop

Figure 3: F-18 Operating Envelope

3. Method

We used the basic procedure presented in [7] to optimize the F-18 controller. For simplicity, we used the same controller structure as the baseline design but made the parameters piecewise constant functions of the scheduling variable. The number and size of the piecewise constant interval was allowed to vary.

The objective function for the optimization was based on the same error definition used in [1]. The relative error of the closed-loop frequency response at some operating point is

$$\tilde{\Delta}_m \doteq (P - P_0)P_0^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where P_0 is the closed inner loop at the nominal operating point, and P is the closed inner loop at the other operating point. As a consequence of Safonov and Chiang's Robustness Theorem [3], the maximum singular value of the relative error must be less than one for stability to be maintained across the operating regime, so the objective of the inner loop controller is to maintain a relative error less than one for all operating points. Therefore, an obvious choice of an optimization function is to minimize the sum of the relative errors over a family of operating points, Eq (2).

$$\begin{aligned} \min J &= \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{\sigma}(\tilde{\Delta}_{m_i}) \\ \text{subject to: } &\bar{\sigma}(\tilde{\Delta}_{m_i}) < 1 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\tilde{\Delta}_m$ is defined in Eq (1), and n is the number of operating points in the design family.¹ The operating points used in evaluating the objective function are the original twelve used for design in [1] plus an additional eight operating points chosen to more uniformly represent the operating envelope as a function of the scheduling variable, dynamic pressure. Consequently, a reduced total relative error results in a more uniform time response across the operating envelope.

We generated two new controllers. First we used the following design variables: the number of intervals in which the scheduling variable range is divided, the endpoints of each interval, and three

¹For n operating points there are only $(n - 1)$ nonzero relative errors, since one of the operating points is the nominal.

controller parameters for each interval. The number of intervals are allowed to vary between 2 and 9, and each interval endpoint is allowed to vary independently within the range of the scheduling variable. The minimum and maximum range of the scheduled control parameters are determined from the initial design performed in [1]. Within each interval, the three control parameters are allowed to vary between their minimum and maximum values independently of each other. For simplicity, the controller parameters are implemented as piecewise constant values for each interval.

Next, we optimized in the same manner with one additional design variable, the central controller. There are a total of twenty operating points in the design family. The additional variable is a pointer which allows the relative error computation to use any of the operating points in the design family as nominal.

4. Results

For the baseline design in [1], the objective function value is 6.4. The closed outer loop time response to a step input at all twenty operating points in the design family are shown in Fig. 4.

The first design reduced the objective function value to 3.2. This is a remarkable 50 per cent reduction in the gain scheduling error. This improved gain schedule resulted in a more consistent time response across the operating envelope when the outer loop is closed. This is clearly shown in Fig. 5.

The second design only adds one more design variable, yet produces significant results. It has an objective function value of 2.2, an additional 30 per cent improvement over the first design. The time response of the same twenty operating points is shown in Fig. 6. There is a substantial improvement over both the baseline and the first design in making the time responses more uniform across the operating envelope.

Figure 4: Baseline Time Response

5. Conclusion

In this paper we have demonstrated that, gain scheduling can be optimized resulting in a more consistent output across the operating envelope. Furthermore, this optimization can be significantly improved by allowing the nominal operating point to vary. This also reduces the burden on the engineer to select a 'good' nominal operating point. Finally, in this application, by having a more consistent, uniform time response across the operating envelope, the pilot workload is reduced, thereby increasing their effectiveness in other operations.

References

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Figure 5: Time Response with Fixed Nominal Point

Figure 6: Time Response with Variable Nominal Point

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